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STUDENTS IN THE STATE OF INDEPENDENT LIVING

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Over the years, professionals across academic and clinical domains have articulated various interpretations of the concept of health. However, the World Health Organization (WHO) has imparted a crucial lesson that health transcends mere absence of disease; rather, it hinges on a multifaceted framework encompassing physical, emotional, mental, and social dimensions. These constituent facets of health carry equal significance, and the deterioration of any one aspect compromises an individual's overall well-being. Consequently, individuals bear the responsibility of nurturing their holistic health, necessitating the cultivation of healthy lifestyle habits. It is evident that lifestyle choices are substantially influenced by a multitude of factors, which pose particular challenges to college students living independently, away from the familial comfort.

One of the primary challenges for Filipino college students engage in self-direct living is financial management. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), the average family income in the Philippines in 2021 was approximately PHP 313,000 annually, with many families struggling to support their children's higher education expenses. The rising cost of tuition, coupled with living expenses such as rent, food, and transportation, imposes a significant burden on students. Apart from the economic pressure and academic demand they faced, students thriving independent living are tasked with sole management of their time, logistical resources, nutrition, stress, sleep patterns, independence, responsibility, psychological and emotional equilibrium, social interactions, and physical activities. In this context, a simple lifestyle survey questionnaire was administered to 86 education college students at State University of Norther Negros who were residing away from their parental homes. This survey shed light on the prevailing lifestyle practices among the respondents. The findings underscored those issues such as poor sleep patterns, dietary choices, financial support and cultural adaptation emerged as the top three challenges faced by students living away from home. Conversely, the impact of academic and school-related activities was notably higher among these students compared to their counterparts living with their families

In conclusion, a healthy lifestyle is the cornerstone of a thriving existence. The cultivation of health-conscious habits, engagement in physical activities, and the avoidance of a sedentary lifestyle are pivotal factors in the success and well-being of college students living independently. While this phase offers opportunities for independence and self-discovery, it also brings forth formidable responsibilities that must

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be surmounted. It is imperative for students to navigate this juncture adeptly, harnessing the potential for personal growth and fostering a productive and health-oriented way of life.

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